

MECHANISMS FOR DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGION AND TOURISM IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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Tourism is one of the fastest growing sectors in the world economy. The average annual growth of the global tourism industry is 4-5% per year. It forms 10 percent of the gross world income. The number of tourists traveling in the world in 2015 was almost a billion, and the income from tourism was \$ 1.3 trillion. The share of tourism in the economies of some foreign countries is more than 50 percent. In particular, 61.0% in Hungary, Greece - 50% in Greece, 53 % in Bahab¹.

According to the World Tourism Organization (JTt), the number of people in the field of tourism is 300 million. The man is close to 8 percent of the world's common employment. The share of exports of tourist services throughout the world is 30%, and 6% on goods and services. In recent years (2000-2016) Despite the progress of the global financial and economic crisis, the high-flagged growth in the macroeconomic indicators is considered as a phenomenon of the end of the period (stick).

The world experience of regional policy is characterized by the existence of the following general trends: decentralization, interregional integration, the environment, welfare, etc.

Currently, the general strategy and specific promotion of regional development in Uzbekistan have not been developed. Mexanizm can be shown to give subventions and dotations to some regions, mainly within the framework of the state budget. Also, state programs of socio-economic development on forecasts of medium-term development of Regions, some regions (sectors) have been developed. There is a government decision to encourage and encourage foreign investment, to give incentives and facilities to the regions in terms of developing small and private business (tourism)².

In foreign countries, many measures are aimed at stimulating economic growth in the regions that are lagging behind in terms of the level of development. These include promoting the deployment of Public Enterprises, increasing the competitiveness and attractiveness of the regions (sectors) through financial and non-financial measures, providing incentives and incentives through budget and tax.

¹ Source: The information of the World Tourism Organization (JTt) is calculated.

² Program of development of the Aral Sea Region development in 2017-2021. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, January 2017 , January18, 2017.

In addition to individual mechanisms of regional policy, there is a widely used mechanisms to develop regional target programs, support border areas, and establish special economic zones and mechanisms.

The development and implementation of strategy and target programs as a mechanism for the development of the region (tourism) in developed European countries is widely used.

Uzbekistan has a certain experience in the development of targeted state programs aimed at developing the regional tourism market as well as at the level of different regions. In particular, the development of annual, medium-term forecasts of development of regions (sectors) and state programs is widely established. For example, in Tashkent, Khorezm and Kashkadarya regions for five years, state programs on the development of tourism are being implemented.

But due to the experience of foreign countries in this direction, some new priority areas can be used. The following table 1 shows the priorities of the tourism development strategy developed in Finland, Turkey and Canada.

1-table.

Specific features of the development of Tourism Development Strategies in foreign countries ³

Strategy development prints	Finland	Turkey	Canada
Taking into account the concept of sustainable development	Subvention of Tourism subjects using new technologies, alternative energy sources, ecological clean water	Application of measures based on sustainable development in the development of tourism, ensuring the integrated development of regions, solving the problem of employment	Using the concept of sustainable development in tourism development
Implementation of innovation	Development of ecotourism	Formation of ten tourist cities, nine tourist recreation zones and seven corridors	Development of ecotourism in the northern regions

³ Valedinskaya E.N. Innovative ASPECTING RESVATION TURZMA V Moskovskom Regione. Moscow, 2011, p 16-20.

The development of tourism development strategy in the region can be widely used by the concept of sustainable UN and the use of innovative technologies proposed by the United Nations.

In the mechanisms regulating region and tourism development, regional and tourism development has also been accumulated. The state management of tourism can be divided into three models. The first model is the lack of a central governing body regulating tourism in the country. At the same time, the main problems of tourism are resolved in the territories of developed countries.

The second model – a separate network of tourism is managed by the ministry. Among such countries it is possible to include Malaysia, Egypt, Bulgaria, Turkey. The main issue is the creation of favorable conditions for attracting tourists, the development of infrastructure facilities.

The public administration is at the disposal of multidisciplinary ministry, which is engaged in ministries, departments and enterprises operating in the tourism market, manufacturing the necessary regulatory documents (Spain, Great Britain, Netherlands).

The main problem in all the above models is the central government, network ministries and enterprises, providing a balance between governing bodies of the region.

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